

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE NETWORKING PLATFORM

Deliverable 5.1

Date: 16 June 2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Technical references

Grant Agreement number:	101035811
Project Acronym:	EELISA InnoCORE
Project title:	EELISA INNOVation and COMmon REsearch strategy
Start date of the project:	1 June 2021
Duration of the project:	36 months

Deliverable No.:	5.1 EELISA innoCORE Networking Platform
Work Package:	5
Task:	5.1 Development of the EELISA innoCORE networking platform
Lead beneficiary:	FAU
Due date of deliverable:	16 June 2023
Actual submission date:	16 June 2023
Dissemination level:	Public

Document history

Version	Date	WP Leader	Reviewed by:
0.1	12 June 2023	FAU	First draft by Tobias Klima (FAU)
0.2	13 June 2023	FAU	Second draft modified following input from EELISA InnoCORE partners
0.3	14 June 2023	SNS	First quality check by Darya Krasilnikov (SNS)
0.4	15 May 2023	FAU	Second quality check
1.0	16 May 2023	FAU	Final version by Tobias Klima (FAU)

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811.

Disclaimer: The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Executive summary

This document is prepared within the work package WP5 – “Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)”, as deliverable D5.1 “EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform” of the project EELISA INNOvation and COmmon REsearch strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA InnoCORE), co-funded by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101035811.

The EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform is designed as a place for researchers to register their research profile and interests. Users can also upload research projects or calls for proposals, based on which, by matching key words with the profiles through an intelligent algorithm, potential cooperation partners are brought together. The EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform is connected to the already established EELISA Community Platform, activating a large potential of users to create research-oriented EELISA Clusters.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Responsibles for the EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform

Partner	Acronym	Contact person for EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	David Schkade (david.schkade@fau.de) Tobias Klima (tobias.klima@fau.de)
Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	SSSA	Sara Barsanti (sara.barsanti@santannapisa.it) Calogero Maria Oddo (calogero.oddo@santannapisa.it)
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Simona Gallerani (simona.gallerani@sns.it) Darya Krasilnikov (darya.krasilnikov@sns.it)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions (alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EINP. EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

R & I. Research and Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Table of Contents

Technical references.....	2
Document history	2
EELISA InnoCORE Partners.....	3
Executive summary.....	4
Responsibles for the EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform	5
Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions (alphabetic order).....	6
Table of Contents.....	7
1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE.....	9
2 General Considerations	11
3 The EELISA innoCORE Networking Platform	12
3.1 Platform functions: The main pillars of the EINP	13
3.1.1 Redirection of users from the EELISA Community Platform.....	14
3.1.2 The platform: user ID	16
3.1.3 The platform: monitoring and clustering functions	22
3.2 Challenges of the EINP.....	25
4 Annex I – Example of matching projects	26

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

List of tables

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders 10
 Table 2: Research projects status 20
 Table 3: Three matched projects with details on scores and labels 21

List of figures

Figure 1: Relation between the EELISA Communities and EELISA Clusters 12
 Figure 2: Screenshot of the “research network” page on the EELISA Community Platform. 15
 Figure 3: Screenshot of the user profile 16
 Figure 4: Screenshot on how to add a project on the platform..... 17
 Figure 5: Screenshot of the list of uploaded projects 17
 Figure 6: Algorithm of the matching function 19
 Figure 7: Screenshot of possible matching for a project with details on score and status.... 20
 Figure 8: Screenshot of two possible matching projects 21
 Figure 9: Clustering Networks 23
 Figure 10: Clustering chord diagram 23

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 45 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project,

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

Table 1 - List of work packages and WP leaders

WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2 General Considerations

The EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform (EINP) has been described in the Grant Agreement as deliverable D5.1. Its purpose is to realize the creation of EELISA clusters, connecting researchers with similar interests and complementary expertise based on potential research projects or calls for proposals for funding. The idea is to use the available information about the researcher's profiles and the projects' objectives and tasks, and to establish a connection between potential cooperation partners by a matching algorithm.

Many researchers from EELISA partners are already registered in the EELISA Community platform, which provides a place for researchers, but also for educators, students, industry stakeholders, and others, to connect on certain (high-level) topics. The EELISA Community platform is open to all interested people, and can be accessed online here: <https://community.eelisa.eu/>.

The login to the Community platform from users affiliated with EELISA partner HEIs is possible via single-sign-on (SSO), i.e., the user can use the same credentials (user name and password) as they use for their local, edugain-compatible identity management. This provides a comfortable way of registration, as some information like name and contact information is already transmitted in the meta-data of the edugain login, but also a first distinction between users from within the alliance and externals is possible.

To enable a simple transition/migration of users to the EINP, it was clear that the large base of already registered users and the user-friendly login shall be exploited. To this end, the description of the deliverable D5.1 envisioned not a separate EINP, but more an EELISA InnoCORE Networking Tool (EINT), which could be fully integrated into the Community Platform. During development, this approach was discarded as incompatibilities between programming languages and potentially difficult requirements on the infrastructure were identified as risks. To mitigate those, it was decided to develop the EINP separately, to give the development the necessary freedom to establish a working solution in a first step, while integrative measures could still be performed in a general overhaul and integration of the EELISA IT systems. From the EELISA Community platform, a redirecting link transmitting required data from the targeted user group ensures the seamless connection between the two solutions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

3 The EELISA innoCORE Networking Platform

In large institutions, and even more so in university alliances, a lack of collaborative research initiatives may reflect a lack of awareness of other researchers working on related topics (<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1213139.pdf>). In this sense, the EELISA InnoCore project offers an institutional support to the creation of EELISA research clusters by the development of a web-based tool for EELISA researchers (hereafter EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform, EINP), which hosts a dynamically-populated database. The EINP allows the researchers of the network to add their profiles and upload possible research activities relevant for dealing with the Societal Challenges identified within the EELISA communities (horizontal aggregations shown in Figure 1), forming research oriented EELISA clusters (vertical aggregations).

Figure 1 - Relation between the EELISA Communities and EELISA Clusters

The proposed research initiatives are characterized by labels that are the input for search and matching functions. The EINP facilitates the identification of common educational, research, and third mission interests within the EELISA network. The goal of this task is to allow EELISA researchers to find their counterparts within the EELISA network and to consequently identify scientific and technological solutions which in turn will be merged in different EELISA InnoCORE clusters. Towards this aim, SSSA and SNS partners cooperated closely with FAU, the latter responsible for setting-up the IT platform for EELISA communities. In particular, FAU created a redirect for the relevant user group, transmitting the required user data to the EINP. The entries of the platform have been defined through a series of WP5 meetings (March 2021-

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

June 2022) during which SNS and SSSA proposed their ideas and the other partners provided their feedback. The actual design of the platform is therefore the result of a refined, collaborative process among the EELISA partners. A very preliminary check of the platform functioning has been carried out by SNS for the creation of the first EELISA Clusters (called "proto-clusters"), described in D5.2. FAU is responsible for the securely encrypted transmission of the user data from the Community Platform to the EINP.

The EINP provides the opportunity to facilitate additional collaborations within and across partners with three main objectives:

1. to facilitate the exchange between academics and researchers within EELISA by connecting individuals with similar research interests;
2. to collect research interests within EELISA in a structured and continuous manner in order to understand which are the main research topics to focus on in the coming years;
3. to create research clusters, connecting universities and research groups in order to identify future trajectories for possible new international research projects and facilitate the creation of new opportunities.

In the EELISA InnoCORE framework related to the vertical and horizontal approach to research, the EINP together with the EELISA Connect Open Calls are the main tools that can facilitate the creation of research clusters.

EELISA InnoCORE intends to enhance its R&I activities through the EINP. Firstly, there is a strong connection with the EELISA Connect Open Calls: researchers can use the platform to search for people interested in their research topics in order to try to organise specific workshops. Similarly, the platform can be a tool for the establishment of new EELISA Communities. On a macro level, the platform aims to provide the EELISA governance with a snapshot of the research areas most studied within the alliance.

3.1 Platform functions: The main pillars of the EINP

The EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform has the following characteristics:

- web-based application, with javascript as a language and a MySQL database schema;
- researcher user database and authentication system (SSO) integrated via API from another application developed by FAU;
- the research idea entered by the researcher is characterised by 'title', 'abstract' (descriptive) and a set of labels that 'classify' the proposed project;
- creation of a controlled dictionary for label management by administrators of the system administrators;
- design and implementation of an algorithm for identifying similar projects with the possibility of different levels (scores) of similarity;

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

- as soon as the system identifies a similarity match between projects, it sends a notice (e.g. by e-mail) to the proposers to give them the opportunity to establish contact;
- researchers receive alerts, consult the projects identified as "similar" and decide to accept/reject the contact;
- researchers using the platform can decide, for privacy reasons, what data to share beyond the minimum set with the platform users, both in terms of personal data and in terms of the projects;
- production of reports of the data in the system (e.g. number of researchers registered, number of projects, number of matches, number of ok / ko acceptance matches, description analysis of main research topics, etc.);
- quantitative and qualitative analysis function of the match algorithms used, based e.g. on the number of ok / ko acceptance matches;
- clustering algorithm refinement, also based on the use of free keywords.

3.1.1 Redirection of users from the EELISA Community Platform

To highlight the possibility of connecting with potential cooperation partners for the researchers, the link to the redirecting page was placed directly in the top-level navigation of the EELISA Community Platform. The "research network" page informs the interested user about the perks of using the EINP by concisely explaining the purpose and function. Additionally, the protection of the user data under GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) of the EU is disclaimed. A screenshot of the page is shown in Figure 2.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

The EELisa Innocore Networking Platform – EINP

Are you interested in finding collaboration and connection with faculty members for your research ideas?
 Do you want to develop new research project or working group on particular fields?
 Use the EINP to share your ideas and check if can collaborate with researchers in the EELisa Alliance.

EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform.

It take only 10 minutes, but the opportunity can have a big impact on your future!

DISCLAIMER: This will transmit personal data, i.e. your name, e-mail address, and affiliation to the platform. All data will be treated according to GDPR.

Figure 2 - Screenshot of the "research network" page on the EELISA Community Platform

When clicking the redirecting link, the code of the platform verifies whether the user is logged in or not. In the latter case, the user is automatically redirected to the login page. If the user is positively logged in, the profile is checked to verify that the user is indeed registered as a researcher, and thus part of the target group of the EINP. Since the EELISA Community Platform is open to a very broad audience, but the EINP shall explicitly connect researchers for joint projects, this selection was deemed necessary. If the user is eligible for using the EINP, the users name, contact e-mail, and affiliation are encrypted (by AES 256, Advanced Encryption Standard), and posted as part of the redirecting URL to the EINP.

Considering the different purposes of the EINP, there are three types of User IDs:

1. the general administrator, with the maximum degree of rights to change the function of the platform; this ID is given to SSSA, SNS, and FAU responsables as well as to the subcontractor that developed the EINP;

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2. the general user, comprised of academicians, researchers, and other research staff who want to use the platform;
3. the user with monitoring functions, comprising SSSA, SNS and FAU responsables who can have access to the internal database generated by the compilation of users, including information on possible matches and clusters in order to build descriptive reports of possible search clusters over time.

3.1.2 The platform: user ID

The main functions of the EINP are the following:

1. a collection of research projects within EELISA through the collection of basic information about research projects, which is based on the labels of deliverable 5.2 (data entry function);
2. the matching function among different uploaded research projects, considering a set of labels;
3. the clustering function for the projects mapped and matched.

To describe the functions of the EINP we use the first collection of research projects related to Deliverable 5.2 (Proto-clusters).

User Profile

Considering the integration into the EELISA Community log in function, the general user has a profile with general information, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Screenshot of the user profile

Collection of research project (data entry function)

With the user ID, every researcher can upload the detailed information about his or her research field and interests considering a list of input variables, some with prefixed labels and some with free text. The variables and labels reflect the input of Deliverable 5.2 on Proto-cluster as following:

- Personal information of the researcher proposing the research project: It includes compulsory entries (name, surname, institutional affiliation, e-mail address) and facultative entries (statement of research interest, link to personal website and/or to laboratories/infrastructures within which the researcher works).
- Research project information: It includes compulsory entries (title of the project, a short (< 1000 characters) abstract of the project (without acronyms), the action that the

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

researcher is proposing, the strategic research area (SRA) and the sustainable development goal (SDG) that the project addresses, ERC and free keywords) and facultative entries (any available laboratory/infrastructure that could be useful for the project, any already existing EELISA Community that is related to the project).

Figure 4 shows the webpage for the input information related to a project. A researcher can upload more than one research project.

Figure 4 - Screenshot on how to add a project on the platform

Once the user has entered all his or her projects, the 'my project' section updates to show the list of projects entered. Figure 5 shows the projects entered.

For each project, the user can see in the menu bar the main details on title, ERC, SDGs SRAs, free label and data creation. Eventually, the “filters” function can help the user to find a specific project using the title as filter.

Title	Label ERC	Label SDG	Label SRA	Label Free	Date created
Promoting social responsibilit...	International relations, global ar	Quality Education - GOAL 4	Digital - 3		12/06/2023
Inclusive Responsible Researc...	Industrial organisation; entrepre	Reduced Inequality - GOAL 10	Social sciences and humanities	development economic g	12/06/2023

Figure 5 - Screenshot of the list of uploaded projects

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Matching function

As the platform begins to collect research projects, the matching function becomes meaningful. We differentiate the matching function, calculating the potential match between projects and researchers, from the matching routine, i.e., how often and when the matching function is executed. The aim of this function is to find possible common projects and research areas between several projects and several researchers. In this sense the function compares the ERC, SRA and SDG labels to check similarities between the projects entered. In particular, the function calculates a score in percentage.

The current algorithm for finding similar projects is structured in the following way (please confer Figure 6).

➤ Inputs

It takes as input the parameters:

- 'min-score': a decimal number between 0 and 1 (inclusive) representing the minimum score for comparing two projects to consider them like each other.
- 'weights': an object containing a weight, i.e., a decimal number between 0 and 1 (inclusive), for each class of label a project may have, to be used in the calculation of the similarity score between two projects. This allows us to assign different importance to different types of labels in the calculation of similarity.
- 'date': creation date of the projects, extracted through the 'Moment.js' library, for which we want to find similar projects.

➤ Procedure

Two queries are made on the database: one to get all projects created during the date given as a parameter, and one to get the remaining projects.

Each project in the first list is compared by similarity with all the other projects in the database, if they belong to different authors (explained later).

For each comparison whose score exceeds the minimum threshold, a match record is created or updated if it already exists in the database, containing the score together with the information from the project comparison.

➤ Comparison and calculation of the similarity score between two projects

This operation is only performed if the authors of the two projects are different and is used to check whether two projects are like each other.

The comparison is made by comparing the labels of the two projects (see Figure 6):

Considering the same label between the two projects (numerator Formula 1), each label is multiplied by the weight assigned to the category of the label by the 'weights' parameter.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

We repeat the same weighted count for the set of unique labels of the two projects (denominator Formula 1) and finally derive the similarity score of the two projects by dividing the first result by the second result.

The matching-score thus obtained is comparable to a Jaccard similarity coefficient, where however different weights are assigned to different label categories depending on how much we want them to influence the score.

➤ Usage

This algorithm is designed to be a routine to be executed at the time of day when the server is at its lowest load.

In this way, each new project entered into the database is compared by similarity with every other project in the database.

$$\text{Matching Score} = \frac{\text{Pr1 Weighted Labels} \cap \text{Pr2 Weighted Labels}}{\text{Pr1 Weighted Labels} \cup \text{Pr2 Weighted Labels}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PrK Weighted Labels} &= \sum_{\text{PrKSRALabels}} \text{SRA Weight} + \sum_{\text{PrKSDGLabels}} \text{SDG Weight} \\ &+ \sum_{\text{PrKERCLabels}} \text{ERC Weight} + \sum_{\text{PrKFreeLabels}} \text{Free Weight} \end{aligned}$$

Pr \square KSRA Labels = set of Project KSRA Labels

Pr \square KSD GLabels = set of Project KSDG Labels

Pr \square KERCLabels = set of Project KERCLabels

Pr \square KFree Labels = set of ProjectK Free Keyword Labels

Figure 6 - Algorithm of the matching function

To see what and how many research projects match with our project, the user ID can link to the section “Matches”, as shown in Figure 7.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Matches

My project	Matched with	Score	Date	Status
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Comparison of heuristic optimization me...	3%	13/06/2023	Accepted
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Creation of mobility packages based on ...	3%	13/06/2023	To be reviewed
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Development of a method for the interco...	3%	13/06/2023	To be reviewed
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Activity chain optimization with mass da...	3%	13/06/2023	New
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	An extended method for the analysis of ...	3%	13/06/2023	New
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Creation of a micromobility index for citi...	3%	13/06/2023	New
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Analysis of travel behaviour and social n...	3%	13/06/2023	New
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Narrative CV	3%	13/06/2023	New
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Ecosystem performances assessment of...	3%	13/06/2023	New
Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Development of an artificial intraurethral ...	3%	13/06/2023	New

Figure 7 - Screenshot of possible matching for a project with details on score and status

For each research project the user can see on the bar the matched projects, the score, and the status. Moreover, there is also the possibility to see the details of each of the matched project. Figure 7 shows the matched projects with a score of 3% that consider only the label on SDGs, goal 11.

The user receives a mail for each proposed matched project, with the basic information and the invitation to check his/her section of possible matches to accept or reject proposals. The user can read and compare details of each research project and decide to: 1. Accept the match (I accept) 2. Not accept the match (I am not interested).

The status of each research project change depending on the users' actions, as show in Table 2.

Table 2 - Research project status

Matches	User 1 (RP A)	User 2 (RP B)	Status
RP A and RP B	No action	No action	New
RP A and RP B	Accepted	No Action	To be review
RP A and RP B	No Action	Accepted	To be review
RP A and RP B	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted

If both researchers accept the match a mail with an alert will be send and the researchers will have the contact details to start a possible collaboration.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Figure 8 - Screenshot of two possible matching projects

The score is itself a first indicator of possible meaningful matches. Here are some examples of good matches with a score more the 20%.

Table resumes the details of the matches with the highest score.

Table 3 - Three matched project with details on scores and labels

Project A	Project B	Score	Matched Labels
Data sonification	Sound of Vision	41%	<p>Culture, creativity and inclusive society - 4</p> <p>Good Health and Well-being - GOAL 3</p> <p>Digital medicine, e-medicine, medical applications of artificial intelligence - LS7_14</p>
Promoting social responsibility of students by embedding service learning within HEIs curricula (ENGAGE STUDENTS)	Team Class Coaching project	33%	<p>Quality Education - GOAL 4</p> <p>International relations, global and transnational governance - SH2_5</p>
BEE GREEN: Enabling participatory activities through the use of mobile technologies to promote 'green' activities	An extended method for the analysis of workplace mobility planning measures	21%	<p>Health - 2</p> <p>Sustainable Cities and Communities - GOAL 11</p>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

			Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy - SH7_6 Energy, transportation and mobility - SH7_9
--	--	--	---

3.1.3 The platform: monitoring and clustering functions

The user with monitoring functions has the possibility to see the database backend of the collected research projects, with the details about matched projects. Moreover, some general reports are generated automatically by the platform.

Monitoring report

A report with general details is generated with the following descriptive statistics:

- number of research projects and details of associated labels (total projects);
- number of matched research project and details of associated labels (accepted from both researchers; accepted status);
- number of matched research projects and details of associated labels (to be review status);
- score details (distribution and associated matched labels);
- labels distribution on SDGs, SRAs and ERC (for each single label);
- textual analysis of free text keywords.

Clustering function

According to the EELISA definition, clusters are research and innovation-based working groups addressing the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities. The main goal of Clusters is to boost the capability of the EELISA network to solve scientific and technological challenges, sharing ideas, methods, labs, funds, manpower.

In this sense, a research cluster is a formally recognised group of researchers whose research expertise is applied either to a common area, field, or theme, or who are involved in a collaborative research project, or set of related projects.

Clustering is the task of assigning a set of objects to groups (in our case, research projects to groups) so that the objects in the same cluster are more similar (according to a predefined property) to each other than to those in other clusters. (<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0159161>)

The EINP has the aim to create research clusters starting from the collection of research projects, at different levels and with a network approach.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

The first level of research clusters is on users' level, considering the matched and accepted research projects. Three examples are reported in annex 1.

Considering a project as the unit of analysis, the EINP can elaborate the research network associated to each project on the matching function and score based. It will probably appear a quite centralized cluster.

Considering the different labels, the EINP can elaborate the research network, clustering the projects on the base of similar labels (single labels or group of similar labels). The research cluster will probably appear as in Figure 9 (networks) or Figure 10 (chord diagram). In Figure 9 the dots represent the projects and the colours represent similar labels, the links represent the matching. In Figure 10 the dots may represent labels (more quoted labels bigger the dots) and the link represent the matching.

Figure 9 - Clustering Networks

Figure 10 - Clustering chord diagram

Projects-Clustering

The matching-fuction described above leads to very accurate matching scores, but the fact that it must be iteratively repeated on all projects in the database (i.e. for each project created

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

on the date given as a parameter, it is executed with all other projects in the database) makes its execution very heavy and not very scalable as the volume of projects increases.

In order to make this process less heavy, we implemented an automatic clustering algorithm.

In particular, we have created software dedicated to clustering, which exposes a RestAPI interface, which can be contacted by including the following information in the request:

- the type of algorithm we want to use for clustering
- the total number of labels in the database for each category of labels
- the group of projects on which we want to find similarities.

The group of projects received are pre-processed to form the data on which the clustering algorithm can work:

- The data from each project is transformed into a single-dimensional numpy-ndarray where the dimension features [number-labels-sra + number-labels-sdg + number-labels-erc + number-labels-free] are produced in the following way:

- the first 'number-labels-sra'-features represent the ids of the SRA category labels present in the project:

- [0]: if the project does not contain an sra-label with $id = position + 1$
- [1 * sra-weight] if the project contains a sra-label with $id = position + 1$

- the following 'number-labels-sdg'-features represent the ids of the SDG-category labels present in the project and have value

- [0]: if the project does not contain a sdg-label with $id = position + 1 - number-labels-sra$
- [1 * sdg-weight] if the project contains the label with $id = position + 1 - number-labels-sra$

- the following 'number-labels-erc'-features represent the ids of the ERC category labels present in the project and have value

- [0]: if the project does not contain an erc-label with $id = position + 1 - number-labels-sra - number-labels-sdg$
- [1 * erc-weight] if the project contains a label with $id = position + 1 - number-labels-sra - number-labels-sdg$

- the following 'number-labels-free'-features represent the ids of the Free-Labels category labels present in the project and have value

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

- [0]: if the project does not contain a free-label with

id = position +1 - number-labels-sra - number-labels-sdg - number-labels-erc

- [1 * free-weight] if the project contains a label with

id = position +1 - number-labels-sra - number-labels-sdg - number-labels-erc

- The vectors (single-dimensional numpy-ndarray) of the individual projects are concatenated along one dimension to form a numpy-ndarray with dimension [number-projects * number-features extracted from each project].

The matrix thus obtained is of the sparse type, i.e. most of it will consist of 0 and a small part of weight values between 0 and 1 (inclusive).

- Depending on the clustering algorithm chosen, if it does not work well on sparse matrices, a further preprocessing step is also performed, in which the features are projected onto a numerically inferior feature space, producing denser matrices on which clustering can work more easily. This is performed using the Sparse Principal Component Analysis technique.

3.2 Challenges of the EINP

The EINP in its 'simplicity' of operation and its user friendliness, has itself a great goal: to connect researchers from a university alliance of thousands of members. In this sense, the tool itself cannot suffice and its goals can only be achieved with a large collection of research projects.

This implies a series of processes and tools necessary for its successful operation, among which are

1. a communication campaign both through the EELISA channels and through the channels of each institution to promote the tool; one can think of dedicated online pages, videos on social channels and dedicated info sessions.
2. an involvement of all levels of governance of both EELISA and the individual institutions and on different occasions aimed at amplifying the message and objectives of the platform;
3. the continuous use of the platform also in phase 2 of EELISA, foreseeing improvements in its functions, integrations with the rest of the platforms, as well as possible artificial intelligence functionalities to refine both the calculation of the matching score and the calculation and representation of clusters.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

4 Annex I – Example of matching projects

FIRST MATCH

Match result Score: 41% Labels:

- Culture, creativity and inclusive society - 4
- Good Health and Well-being - GOAL 3
- Digital medicine, e-medicine, medical applications of artificial intelligence - LS7_14

Project A Data sonification

Owner

(SNS)

SRA Labels

- Culture, creativity and inclusive society - 4

SDG Labels

- Good Health and Well-being - GOAL 3

ERC Labels

- Digital medicine, e-medicine, medical applications of artificial intelligence - LS7_14

Action Proposed

Scientific collaboration, Exchange of students, Exchange of staff

Abstract

To make accessible to the general public the complex topic of Cosmology, we will transform both observational and synthetic data into video and sounds by means of Data Visualization and Data Sonification techniques. Data Sonification refers to the auditory equivalent of Data visualization, and it has recently received great interest from the scientific and general public, since it greatly contributes to making the dissemination experience completely immersive. Data sonification has several interesting applications, as for example: (i) it helps reaching visually impaired public during dissemination events; (ii) if applied to medical data (heart rate, ECG signals, heart rate variations during exercise), it can become a useful tool in the context of the rapid development of wearable devices for monitoring various physiological parameters; (iii) if applied to seismic data, can provide a fascinating and instructive complement to the “wiggly line” representation of earthquake time series used in the classical seismogram.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Project B Sound of Vision

Owner

(UPB)

SRA Labels

- Culture, creativity and inclusive society - 4

SDG Labels

- Good Health and Well-being - GOAL 3

ERC Labels

- Digital medicine, e-medicine, medical applications of artificial intelligence - LS7_14

Free Labels

- medical engineering and technology
- sound using digital tools

Action Proposed

Scientific collaboration, Exchange of students, Exchange of staff

Abstract

Sound of Vision will design, implement and validate an original non-invasive hardware and software system to assist visually impaired people by creating and conveying an auditory representation of the surrounding environment. This representation will be created, updated and delivered to a blind person continuously and in real time. This system will help visually impaired people in any kind of environment (indoor/outdoor), without the need for predefined tags/sensors located in the surroundings.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

SECOND MATCH

Match result Score: 33% Labels:

- Quality Education - GOAL 4
- International relations, global and transnational governance - SH2_5

Project A

Promoting social responsibility of students by embedding service learning within HEIs curricula (ENGAGE STUDENTS)

Owner

Gabriel Dima (UPB)

SRA Labels

- Digital - 3

SDG Labels

- Quality Education - GOAL 4

ERC Labels

- International relations, global and transnational governance - SH2_5

Action Proposed

Scientific collaboration, Exchange of students, Exchange of staff

Abstract

The ENGAGE STUDENTS project focuses on social responsibility of higher education institutions at student and teacher level. Strengthening the social dimension in education has been an important European priority (COM(2006) 208 final, 2013/C 168/02), that has been accentuated even further by the Commission in the renewed EU agenda for Higher Education. Innovative curricula and teaching approaches are seen to contribute to reducing the current high-level skills gap between students and labour market needs. Especially the integration of extra-curricular experience into study programmes is identified as solution for enhancing students' transversal skills, better preparing them for finding a job (COM(2017) 247 final). The project general objective is to empower the social dimension of higher education by increasing its relevance for society through embedding service-learning as a common pedagogical approach within education and research practice. The project specific objectives are as follows:- to explore the existing methodology of service-learning and other forms of community-related learning and research- to develop a methodological toolkit and a pedagogical workbook to be used by teachers- to build the critical mass of knowledge and resources in partner HEIs in order to foster the use of service learning and other community-related learning methodologies.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Project B

Team Class Coaching project

Owner

Dana Corina Deselnicu (UPB)

SRA Labels

- Social sciences and humanities - 8

SDG Labels

- Quality Education - GOAL 4

ERC Labels

- International relations, global and transnational governance - SH2_5

Free Labels

- social policies
- work and welfare

Action Proposed

Scientific collaboration, Exchange of students, Exchange of staff

Abstract

ThiFa project will develop the tools necessary for skills enhancement, targeted to higher education, which will enhance better knowledge transfer where transforming a class into team, is very important in effective learning.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

THIRD MATCH

Match result Score: 21% Matched Labels:

- Health - 2
- Sustainable Cities and Communities - GOAL 11
- Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy - SH7_6
- Energy, transportation and mobility - SH7_9

Project A

BEE GREEN: Enabling participatory activities through the use of mobile technologies to promote 'green' activities

Owner

(ITU)

SRA Labels

- Health - 2
- Digital - 3

SDG Labels

- Sustainable Cities and Communities - GOAL 11
- Responsible Consumption and Production - GOAL 12

ERC Labels

- Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy - SH7_6
- Energy, transportation and mobility - SH7_9

Free Labels

- Smart City
- Public Participation
- Sustainability
- Recycle/Reuse

Action Proposed

Scientific collaboration, Exchange of students, Exchange of staff

Abstract

The aim of this project is to use existing 'smart city' platforms to create par

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Project B

An extended method for the analysis of workplace mobility planning measures

Owner

(Budapest University of Technology and Economics)

SRA Labels

- Health - 2

SDG Labels

- Sustainable Cities and Communities - GOAL 11

ERC Labels

- Social influence; power and group behaviour - SH3_6
- Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy - SH7_6
- Cities; urban, regional and rural studies - SH7_7
- Energy, transportation and mobility - SH7_9

Free Labels

- measure
- mobility planning

Action Proposed

Scientific collaboration, Exchange of students, Exchange of staff, Partnership

Abstract

An extended method for the analysis of workplace mobility planning measures

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811